

HOW DO WE INVEST IN SOCIAL CAPITAL? THE IFUGAO CULTURAL EXPERIENCES

MORAYA P. CACLINI

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4881-1342>

caclinimoraya@gmail.com

Ifugao State University, Lagawe Campus, Lagawe, Ifugao, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Social capital is a lot like real capital where more money a person or a society makes them invest in things easier and better off people they are. The purpose of the study is to measure how and why do Ifugao keeps on investing in social capital especially in their cultural practices. The research design used is both qualitative and quantitative where ethnography is a qualitative design in the sense that focuses on describing the investing social capital in terms of the three categories such as bonding, bridging, and linking on their selected Ifugao cultural experiences such as birthday, engagement, marriage, and death. Quantitative research design is used in the frequency distribution and percentages on respondents' profiles. Thematic analysis is used to analyze the focused-group discussion among key informants from performers and participants' cultural experiences. Findings revealed that most performers and participants are above 55 years old, male, married, college graduate, government employee, and above 40,000 Php monthly income. The majority of the performers experienced Ifugao birthday, engagement, marriage, and death wherein it has non-monetary value benefits such as it creates strong bonding among family and close friends, bridging connections with distant friends, and linking relationships with other participants. The monetary value that investing in social capital creates high cost, high return, high effort in marriage, while low cost and high return in death. On the other hand, most of the participants experienced the same with that of performers in Ifugao cultures. Based on the findings, the social capital investment model is developed to serve as a guide for Ifugaos in performing and participating in the cultures. Therefore, Ifugao Tawali tribes should invest in social capital to build stronger bonding, connections, trust, and reciprocity among their family, friends, and communities.

Keywords: social capital, investment, non-monetary value, monetary value, ethnography, Ifugao cultures